

ANALYSIS OF THE ACTIVITIES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN IN IMPLEMENTING INTERNATIONAL LAW IN THE FIELD OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

Nabiev firuzjon khamidovich

PhD in Law

E-mail: firuzlegalaid@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18444317>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 29st January 2026

Accepted: 30th January 2026

Online: 31th January 2026

KEYWORDS

implementation, international law, intellectual property, Republic of Uzbekistan, international treaties, national legislation, transformation, harmonization, legal regulation, WIPO

ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan in implementing international legal norms in the field of intellectual property into its national legal system. It examines the legal and institutional foundations for fulfilling international obligations arising from Uzbekistan's participation in international treaties and international organizations related to intellectual property. Special attention is paid to the methods and forms of implementation of international legal norms, including the adoption of domestic legislative acts, transformation, and indirect harmonization. The study analyzes the national legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan governing the protection of intellectual property objects, as well as the practice of applying international treaty norms. The author concludes that the adoption of domestic legal acts is the primary and most widely used method of implementing international norms in the field of intellectual property, while emphasizing the need to improve monitoring and coordination mechanisms for their execution..

The implementation of international intellectual property law is a complex and multidimensional phenomenon, embodying international obligations within a state's domestic legal system. Thus, ensuring the implementation of certain humanitarian provisions requires coordination between authorized intellectual property authorities. The implementation mechanism involves the transformation and adaptation of the norms of one legal system to those of another. The transformation of norms adopted from another legal system has the following consequence: the transition from an international to a national legal system primarily involves changes in the content of the legal provisions governing intellectual property.

International treaties to which the Republic of Uzbekistan is a party apply to relations related to the regulation of exclusive rights to the results of intellectual activity and associated means of individualization, except in cases where an international treaty requires the adoption of a domestic act (indirect unification). The essence of indirect unification is that states party to such an international treaty are obligated to establish in their domestic legislation a more or less detailed legal regime established in this Treaty.

Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On International Treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated 06.02.2019 No. ZRU-518 establishes that “International treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan, along with generally recognized principles and norms of international law, are an integral part of the legal system of the Republic of Uzbekistan” [1].

It is important to note that the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the procedure for preparing draft international treaties and fulfilling the obligations of the Republic of Uzbekistan under international treaties” dated December 12, 2000 No. 473 is one of the main by-laws for the implementation of this norm.

In legal-scientific practice and theory, a number of methods of implementing international legal principles and norms in the national legislative system are distinguished. Developing this idea, we turn to the opinion of M. I. Abdullayev, who notes that “In order to include international legal norms in domestic law and harmonize them, the legislator takes a number of measures. They are quite diverse. In legal literature, they are called: 1) reference; 2) reception; 3) unification; 4) transformation; 5) creation of a special legal regime; 6) cancellation of domestic acts that contradict international obligations” [2].

It should be noted that if states fail to comply with their international obligations, implementation loses its effectiveness, which immediately impacts international legal regulation itself. Therefore, there is a pressing need to create conditions for the use of various legal tools that will subsequently form a specific mechanism for implementing international intellectual property law into national legislation.

Over the past years, Uzbekistan has reformed its legal framework to support the protection of intellectual property rights. The first significant step was the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Copyright and Related Rights” dated August 30, 1996, No. 272-I (new version of this law dated July 20, 2006, No. ZRU-42), followed by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Inventions, Utility Models and Industrial Designs” dated August 29, 2002, No. 397-II and the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Trademarks, Service Marks and Appellations of Origin of Goods” dated August 30, 2001, No. 267-II, which laid the foundation for the protection of intellectual property in Uzbekistan, but required further alignment with international standards.

In this regard, it is important to note that the legislative branch of the Republic of Uzbekistan has determined that the provisions of international treaties on intellectual property protection are implemented through the adoption of domestic legislation. Uzbekistan's legislative practice shows that there are no provisions mandating the implementation of the provisions of ratified international treaties, with the exception of those rules recognizing the priority of international treaties.

Accordingly, there are international and national methods of applying international law. Both methods are interconnected. In both, the state occupies a central position.

The interaction between two normative entities — national and international law — loses its functional nature when international law effectively penetrates the national legal system. This phenomenon occurs because the effect of any international normative legal act is to achieve a certain degree of regulation of certain relations arising between certain entities within the domestic system (international legal regulation of human rights, the procedure for

concluding and executing foreign economic transactions, the protection of intellectual property rights, etc.).

Our scientific position on this issue coincides with the opinion of V.V. Gavrilov, who noted that “In accordance with the theory of implementation, the essence is not in the transfer of the norms of international law to the norms of national legal order, but in the application of the former within a given state with the sanction of the latter. In those cases where national law sanctions the application of the rules of international treaties within the country, the problem of so-called self-executing and non-self-executing treaties arises” [3].

A non-self-executing intellectual property treaty is sanctioned by the state, and its full and flawless implementation requires a national legislative act that will detail the content of the aforementioned provisions. Such internal acts are discussed in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On International Treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan”. This requirement can be justified by the fact that non-self-executing international intellectual property treaties define the generally accepted framework of conduct within which states establish the rights and obligations of subjects of national intellectual property law. The above-mentioned international treaties are usually legitimized to achieve a certain regulation of relations within the country.

Of course, the unique nature of intellectual property rights is reflected in their territorial nature. According to Article 7 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, if an international treaty or agreement establishes rules completely different from those provided for by civil law, the rules of the international treaty or agreement apply.

We believe it is important to draw attention to the fact that, according to the list of state bodies and other organizations responsible for fulfilling obligations under international treaties and membership of the Republic of Uzbekistan, approved by the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to improve the procedure for fulfilling obligations arising from international treaties and membership of the Republic of Uzbekistan in international organizations” dated June 22, 2020 No. PP-4756, “The Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the state body responsible for fulfilling obligations under international treaties and membership of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the World Intellectual Property Organization and the International Union for the Protection of New Varieties of Plants” [4].

Based on this, we consider it appropriate to supplement the list of organizations in the field of intellectual property based on the fact that the Republic of Uzbekistan is a member of the Interstate Council for the Protection of Intellectual Property (MGSIS) in accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 1, 2011 No. PP-1591 “On approval of an international treaty” approved the Agreement on cooperation in the field of legal protection and protection of intellectual property and the creation of the Interstate Council on legal protection and protection of intellectual property, signed at a meeting of the Council of Heads of Government of the CIS member states on November 19, 2010 in the city of St. Petersburg.

When analyzing the current legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan regulating intellectual property, it is important to note that the regulations do not clearly define which government agency monitors the implementation of international agreements on intellectual

property protection. Specifically, Parts 17-18, Clause 9 of the Regulation “On the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan” approved by the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On organizational measures to further improve the activities of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated April 13, 2018, No. PP-3666, defines two tasks in the field of intellectual property regulation:

A) development of a unified state policy in the field of intellectual property and protection of rights to inventions, trademarks, copyrights and rights to other intellectual property

B) legal protection of inventions, utility models, industrial designs, trademarks and other intellectual property objects.

Subparagraph 17 of paragraph 10 of this Regulation defines the functions of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the area of developing a unified state policy in the field of intellectual property, as well as protecting rights to inventions, trademarks, copyright and other intellectual property.

The development of national legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan facilitates the state's participation in universal and regional international organizations, where membership in WIPO occupies a special place.

To summarize the above, we can conclude that the adoption of a domestic act is the most common method for implementing the provisions of international intellectual property treaties, chosen by the legislative branch of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The process of transformation, that is, the transfer of obligations assumed by Uzbekistan, is primarily carried out through the institution of implementation. Having studied Uzbekistan's legislative practice, we have concluded that it lacks provisions mandating the implementation of the provisions of ratified international treaties, with the exception of those rules recognizing the priority of international treaties.

List of references:

1. <https://lex.uz/docs/4193763>
2. Abdullayev M. I. Coordination of domestic law with international law (theoretical aspects) // Jurisprudence. - 1993. - No. 2.- P. 49.
3. Gavrilov V.V. International mechanism for monitoring the implementation of universal human rights instruments // Moscow Journal of International Law. 1995. No. 4. P. 24-37.
4. <https://lex.uz/docs/4866232> (National Legislation Database, June 23, 2020, No. 07/20/4756/07953)